

D2.3. ANNUAL WORK PROGRAMME YEAR 2

Region Dalarna (DAL)

30.11.25

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Project coordinator	Delia Sola Giménez (GN)

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Deliverable information	
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	Name of the Entity	Acronym	Role	Country	ORG Type
1	Government of Navarra	GN	C	ES	PB
2	Development Society of Navarra	SODENA	B	ES	SME
3	Northern Netherlands Alliance	SNN	B	NL	PB
4	Province Groningen	GRO	B	NL	PB
5	Province Fryslan	FRY	B	NL	PB
6	Province Drenthe	DTH	B	NL	PB
7	University of Groningen	UGRO	B	NL	UNI
8	Fryslan Innovation Foundation	IPF	B	NL	NGO
9	Region Dalarna	DAL	B	SE	PB
10	Region Värmland	VÄR	B	SE	PB
11	Region Gävleborg	GÄV	B	SE	PB
12	Region Normandie	NOR	B	FR	PB
14	Service Public de Wallonie	SPW	B	BE	PB
15	Innovation Agency Lithuania	IAL	B	LT	PB
16	Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council	HURC	B	FI	PB
17	Scottish Enterprise	SE	B	UK	PB
18	University of Strathclyde	IBioIC	B	UK	UNI
19	Association of Cities and Regions for Sustainable Resource Management	ACR+	B	BE	OTH
<p>*Legend = Role in the Project: C – Coordinator // B – Beneficiary // AP – Associated Partner // Organization Type: RTD – Research and Technological Development // UNI – Higher or secondary education establishment // SME – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // NGO – Non-Governmental Org // PB – Public Body // OTH – Other</p>					

Work Packages Name		WP Leader
WP 1	Project Management	GN
WP 2	Design of transformative innovation program and regional action plans for circular for interconnected Regional Innovation Valleys	DAL
WP 3	Creation of the Circular Economy “Dance Floor” (Regional Ecosystems’ mobilisation, dynamization, connection)	SNN
WP 4	Competitive selection and funding of interregional innovation projects	NOR
WP 5	Innovation Valley Results sustainability and replication. Roadmap for the future and outreachment of new Circular Valleys	ACR+
WP 6	Dissemination and Communication	IAL

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS.....	5
1. Executive Summary	6
1.1. Annual Work Programme (AWP) objectives	6
2. Expected impacts.....	6
2.1. Interconnected, Inclusive, and More Efficient Innovation Ecosystems	6
2.2. Enhance Cross-Border Network Connectivity and Inter-Regional Collaboration	7
2.3. Strengthen and Expand Cooperation Between Innovation Ecosystems Worldwide	7
2.4. Foster More Inclusive and Gender-Equal Innovation Ecosystems.....	7
2.5. Reducing Territorial Inequalities in Access to Innovation Support	7
3. Correspondence with part B of the proposal	8
4. Annual Work Programme Activities.....	9
4.1. Annual Work Programme	9
4.1.1. Structure of the Annual Work Programme	9
4.1.2. Timing of the different programmed activities and their components (Gantt chart)	9
4.1.3. Detailed work description.....	11
4.1.4. Continuous monitoring	18
4.2. Participation in Annual Work Programme activities.....	19
4.3. Resources to be committed.....	20
4.3.1. Summary effort table.....	20

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
CE	Circular Economy
AWP	Annual Work Programme
CAB	Call Advisory Board
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CE	Circular Economy
CSC	Call Steering Committee
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
ECIV	European Circular Innovation Valley
ERRIN	European Regions Research and Innovation Network
EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
EU	European Union
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties (Cascade Funding)
GA	Grant Agreement
ISDT	Interregional Strategy Design Team
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MGA	Model Grant Agreement
OC	Open Call
PC	Project Coordinator
RIV	Regional Innovation Valleys
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SMG	Submission Group
TC	Project Technical Coordinator
TIP	Transformative Innovation Programme
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

1.1. Annual Work Programme (AWP) objectives

The main objective of the second AWP of the ECIV project is to move from preparation to implementation, translating the analytical, methodological, and coordination efforts of the first year into concrete interregional actions and funded innovation initiatives. Building on the foundations established in Year 1: development of the Transformative Innovation Programme (TIP), the definition of 12 interregional missions and sub-missions, and the creation of the Circular Innovation Valley Office, the focus of this second year will be on activating the Dance Floor, consolidating regional and interregional communities, and launching the first Open Call for Innovation Projects as well as the Experimentation Fund, and the preparation of the 2nd Open Call.

At the same time, the project will continue to strengthen regional capacities and governance mechanisms, finalising the Regional Action Plans and advancing the Policy Innovation Platform to ensure long-term impact. Communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities will intensify to enhance the project's visibility and to support the co-creation and mobilisation of consortia around circular value chains.

An important structural change introduced at the beginning of this period is the withdrawal of MIGB partner. Its departure has been managed through the amendment process, and the corresponding budget will be reallocated to activities that strengthen ECIV's strategic areas, particularly entrepreneurship, Deep Tech, and open innovation or to a new project partner to ensure the FSTP budget mobilisation and increase the ECIV circular European ecosystem.

The Year 2 objectives remain fully aligned with ECIV's expected outcomes: the development of a connected, mission-oriented network of circular innovation ecosystems, the activation of cross-regional collaborations, and the mobilisation of public and private investments driving Europe's transition towards a circular and human-centric industry.

2. Expected impacts

2.1. Interconnected, Inclusive, and More Efficient Innovation Ecosystems

During the second year, ECIV will continue to strengthen the interconnections established between regional circular innovation ecosystems, focusing on consolidating the Valley network and deepening collaboration among regional actors. Building on the analyses and data harmonisation completed in Year 1, further efforts will be directed towards integrating findings

into the Transformative Innovation Programme (TIP) and the Regional Action Plans, ensuring coherence between regional and interregional objectives. These activities will promote more efficient knowledge exchange, facilitate the participation of new stakeholders – including SMEs and rural actors – and foster a culture of systemic collaboration across all ECIV regions.

2.2. Enhance Cross-Border Network Connectivity and Inter-Regional Collaboration

With the methodological groundwork completed, Year 2 will focus on the activation of cross-regional missions and submissions and the implementation of the first Open Call for Innovation Projects. The launch of this call, combined with the operationalisation of the Experimentation Fund, will enable the creation of tangible interregional innovation partnerships and pilot projects. The Circular Innovation Valley Office will continue to play a central role in guiding coordination, matchmaking, and knowledge transfer, thereby reinforcing interregional capacity and supporting the green and digital transitions that underpin the EU’s open strategic autonomy.

2.3. Strengthen and Expand Cooperation Between Innovation Ecosystems Worldwide

As ECIV’s interregional cooperation matures, Year 2 will also initiate the first steps towards international collaboration by identifying and engaging external regions and networks beyond the consortium, particularly through links with CCRI, ACR+, and other European and global circular economy initiatives. Shared circular challenges and best practices identified through the Dance Floor will serve as a foundation for future cross-border partnerships and global dialogue on circular innovation.

2.4. Foster More Inclusive and Gender-Equal Innovation Ecosystems

Inclusiveness remains a cross-cutting objective in Year 2. The analysis of regional innovation systems and the governance mechanisms embedded in the TIP will continue to integrate gender equality and diversity considerations, ensuring balanced participation in stakeholder groups, events, and funded projects. WP6 communication activities will also highlight the role of women and underrepresented groups in circular innovation, fostering visibility and inclusiveness across ECIV ecosystems.

2.5. Reducing Territorial Inequalities in Access to Innovation Support

By deploying the first Open Call and Experimentation Fund, ECIV will begin to reduce territorial disparities in access to innovation support, offering tailored opportunities for both advanced

and less mature regions. The Circular Innovation Valley Office will provide guidance and technical assistance to ensure that all regional actors – regardless of size or experience – can participate in ECIV initiatives. These mechanisms will strengthen cohesion between regions and reinforce the overall objective of building a balanced, inclusive, and interconnected European Circular Innovation Valley.

3. Correspondence with part B of the proposal

The activities planned for the second year of ECIV continue to follow the project’s original methodology as described in Part B of the proposal. After a first year focused on analysis, methodological development, and ecosystem mobilisation, the project will now advance into the implementation and experimentation phases of its mission-oriented approach.

Following the established sequence, the work in WP2 will consolidate the outcomes of the analyses conducted in Year 1 by finalising the Transformative Innovation Programme (TIP) and the Regional Action Plans, translating the identified submissions into actionable strategies and governance models. In parallel, WP3 will move into the full deployment of the Dance Floor, bringing regional and interregional stakeholders together to co-develop challenges and collaboration projects under shared circular economy submissions.

The next methodological step, phase 4 of the project, will begin with the launch of the first Open Call for Innovation Projects under WP4 and the Experimentation Fund. This will enable the first practical applications of ECIV’s systemic innovation framework and the mobilisation of public and private investments in circular industrial value chains.

Throughout this period, the project will also increase its activity in knowledge sharing, communication and dissemination through WP6, ensuring that the lessons learned from the ECIV model can be replicated and transferred to other regions in Europe. By following this coherent pathway from analysis to experimentation and replication, ECIV remains aligned with the objectives set out in the Grant Agreement – to foster mission-oriented, interconnected regional innovation valleys and strengthen Europe’s transition toward a circular, human-centric, and resilient industry.

4. Annual Work Programme Activities

4.1. Annual Work Programme

4.1.1. Structure of the Annual Work Programme

The second AWP builds upon the analytical and coordination efforts carried out during the first year and is structured around two main blocks of activities, reflecting the project's transition from preparation to implementation.

The first block focuses on consolidating and applying the analytical and strategic outputs developed in Year 1. This includes finalising the Transformative Innovation Programme (TIP), completing the Joint Circular Economy Action Plan and the Regional Action Plans, and ensuring that all missions and submissions are clearly translated into actionable strategies. These plans will serve as the operational framework guiding the first Open Call for Innovation Projects and the Experimentation Fund, which will be launched during this second year.

The second block is dedicated to the activation and coordination of regional and interregional ecosystems through the full deployment of the Dance Floor methodology. This phase will connect and operationalise the communities identified during the first year, structuring them into thematic and mission-oriented groups that collaborate to co-design innovation projects addressing circular challenges. The Circular Innovation Valley Office will continue to facilitate these exchanges, ensuring coherence between regional initiatives and interregional missions and submissions.

In addition, the AWP reflects the updated consortium composition following the withdrawal of MIGB, which has been addressed through the amendment process. This change does not alter the project's structure but requires internal adjustments in planning and budget allocation across work packages.

Together, these two blocks of work mark ECIV's transition towards a more operational phase, transforming the analytical work of the first year into tangible actions, collaborations, and innovation projects that will drive the circular transformation across European regions.

4.1.2. Timing of the different programmed activities and their components (Gantt chart)

The following table shows the different activities that the project is going to develop in the second year. This Annual Work Plan will define and develop more the kind of activities that will be implemented under the thematic WPs in the WP2- WP3, WP4 and WP6.

ECIV WORK PACKAGE STRUCTURE		DURATION YEAR 2											
		13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
WP1	Management and coordination												
T1.1	Project Management Plan												
T1.2	Administrative, legal and financial coordination and EU communication												
T1.3	Project coordination and implementation												
T1.4	Consortium meetings coordination												
WP2	Design of transformative innovation program and regional action plans for circular for interconnected Regional Innovation Valleys												
T2.1	Analysis and diagnosis to define priorities and gaps												
T2.2	Creation of ECIV office												
T2.3	Design of a Transformative Innovation program and regional action plans												
T2.4	Capabilities and Capacities on regional platforms and Innovation offices												
T2.5	Redefinition and internationalise value chains												
WP3	Creation of a Circular economy Valleys Dance Floor												
T3.1	Creating a "DIALOGUE SPACE" to mobilize and engage the regional ecosystems												
T3.2	Creating the "CHALLENGE SPACE" to orient the connections towards collaborations												
T3.3	Creating the "DEVELOPMENT SPACE": Search and acceleration of solutions to specific challenges												
WP4	Competitive selection and funding of interregional innovation projects												
T4.1	Open calls priorities definition												
T4.2	Preparation and management of Open Calls Innovation Projects												
T4.3	Design and management of an Open Experimentation fund for collaboration												
T4.4	Follow-up and monitoring of funded projects and funding activities												
T4.5	Development and maintenance of tools as funding supporting activity												
WP5	Innovation Valley Results sustainability and replication. Roadmap for the future and outreachment of new Circular Valleys												
T5.1	Literature review/desk research to develop a critical strategy to replicate project results												
T5.2	Mapping the project results for exploitation and replication and identifying the target groups												
T5.3	Regions and Cities Community of Practice												
T5.4	Peer to peer exchange programme												
T5.4	Development of the white book of Regional Innovation Valleys												

WP6	Dissemination and communication, strategy											
T6.1	Deployment Communication & Dissemination plan											
T6.2	Implementation of D&C activities to outreach ECIV's partners scope											
T6.3	Implementation of D&C activities in each ECIV's regions											
T6.4	Communication and dissemination of funding activities											

4.1.3. Detailed work description

WPI: Project management (L: GN) [M1 – M60]

T1.1 Project Management Plan (L: GN; P: SODENA; M1–M60)

This task is already completed. Not activities planned for the upcoming months, although the PMP will be updated according to the Amendment, in case it is needed.

1.2 Administrative, legal, and financial management, reporting support & EU Commission communication (Leader: GN; Participants: ALL; M1–M60)

The coordination team will continue providing comprehensive administrative and financial management support to all partners. Particular attention will be paid to those partners managing co-funding via Structural Funds, such as IAL and the NNL, ensuring that all processes remain aligned with Horizon Europe financial regulations. In parallel, regular communication will be maintained with the Project Officer to finalise the amendment process and ensure the project's continuous alignment with the broader RIV initiative.

T.1.3 Project coordination and implementation (L: GN; P: ALL; M1–M60)

Similar to last period, the coordination team will focus on ensuring the smooth implementation of the Annual Work Plan. Regular Technical Committee meetings (twice per month) will continue to monitor progress and identify potential risks or delays. The coordination team will closely monitor interdependencies, especially between WP2, WP3, and WP4, to maintain coherence between the strategic, operational, and funding-related dimensions of the project. Risks, KPIs and milestones will be continuously updated to reflect the project's progress, and an internal deliverable review system will be maintained to guarantee the quality and consistency of all submissions.

T.1.4 Consortium meetings coordination & attendance (L: GN; P: ALL; MI–M60)

WPI will continue to coordinate the organisation of consortium meetings and other project events. The fourth Consortium Meeting, planned in Normandy for spring 2026, will focus on reviewing progress in the deployment of the Dance Floor, the execution of the first Open Call, and the development of the Regional Action Plans. A General Assembly will be held alongside the consortium meeting to review the overall financial situation. The coordination team will also provide organisational support for ECIV's participation in external dissemination and networking events, ensuring consistent and coordinated representation of the project.

WP2: Design of Transformative Innovation Programme and Regional Action Plans for an Interconnected Regional Innovation Valley (L: DAL) [MI–M60]

T2.1 Analysis and diagnosis to define priorities and gaps (L: DAL; P: ALL)

This task is already completed. Dissemination of the results will be delivered.

T2.2 Creation and coordination of the Circular Innovation Valley Office (L: SODENA; P: ALL)

The ECIV Valley Office, established in Year 1, will continue to act as a central coordination and knowledge-sharing hub, ensuring the coherence of submissions and regional action plans. During this second year, the Office will implement a more systematic approach to interregional dialogue, matchmaking, and mutual learning. The Matchmaking Platform will be fully operationalised to support the mobilisation of innovation consortia across regions. The Valley Office will act as a coordination and alignment hub between WP2, WP3, and WP4, helping to connect strategic objectives with stakeholder mobilisation and funding mechanisms.

T2.3 Design and implementation of the Transformative Innovation Programme (TIP) and Regional Action Plans (L: DAL; P: ALL)

In Year 2, the Transformative Innovation Programme (TIP) has been fully designed and delivered (Month 14). The focus now shifts from design to operationalisation, ensuring that all partners develop a shared understanding of the TIP and feel confident applying its methods in practice. This includes building understanding and co-ownership of the mission-oriented approach across regions, strengthening commitment to the shared goals, and supporting partners as they integrate TIP principles into their regional work, their collaboration across work packages, and their participation in interregional activities.

WP2 will lead the development and delivery of the eight Regional Action Plans, including the Theories of Change for the submissions. Each partner region commits to these plans, which will be aligned with the Transformative Innovation Programme (TIP). WP2 will work closely with WP3 on the development of the interregional Action Plan and the interregional ToCs to ensure coherence between regional and interregional activities.

The Interregional Strategy Design Team will reconvene in Year 2 to discuss how it can continue contributing to ECIV's emerging governance approach and to the ongoing development of the TIP. The team provides a necessary shared space for partners to reflect together, align their work, and keep the TIP active as a collaborative framework that evolves through experience.

T2.4 Capabilities and capacities on regional platforms and innovation offices (L: SODENA; P: ALL)

During the second year, the activities under Task 2.4 will focus on capacity-building, learning, and co-design processes to strengthen regional innovation platforms and offices. Building on the survey and methodological frameworks produced in the first year, WP2 will continue developing the Policy Innovation Platform, which will act as a collaborative space for reflection and mutual learning among regional authorities and ecosystem actors. The work will concentrate on defining the modules and tools for capacity and capability building (D2.8) and on establishing the Policy Innovation Platform (D2.9), both to be delivered by Month 24.

Close collaboration will be maintained with WP3's Dance Floor activities to ensure that lessons and insights emerging from stakeholder engagement and interregional collaboration feed directly into the co-design of governance and policy support tools. Through these combined efforts, Task 2.4 will enhance the institutional capacities of ECIV partners and contribute to the development of shared approaches to mission-oriented governance and systemic circular innovation across the regions.

Additionally, several collaborations have been foreseen with external companies to, along with SODENA, develop training modules for regional governments for the implementation of the place-based missions towards the Circular Economy Transition and to develop a methodology for the evaluation of the current capacities and competencies of the different partner regions.

T2.5 Redefinition and internationalisation of value chains (L: DAL; P: ALL)

In Year 2, T2.5 will lay the foundation for the redefinition and internationalisation of value chains by analysing how selected circular economy value chains are evolving in Europe and internationally. Building on the regional analyses and mappings from Year 1, the task will map

relevant international networks, clusters, and reference initiatives to identify trends, good practices, and potential complementarities that can inform the Transformative Innovation Programme (TIP). WP2 will also develop initial criteria for recognising international ecosystems that align with ECIV's missions and submissions, and may explore light, preliminary outreach to deepen understanding of international perspectives. WP2 will collaborate with WP3 and insights from this work will be shared with WP3 to support the Dance Floors, helping partners contextualise submissions within broader international developments. The focus will be on contributing to the conceptual groundwork for the Policy Innovation Platform, ensuring that its future design is aligned with TIP and responsive to the emerging needs of regions and missions.

WP3: Creation of the Circular Economy “Dance Floor” (Regional Ecosystems’ mobilization, dynamization, connection) (L: SNN) [M3 – M60]

T3.1: Creating a “DIALOGUE SPACE” to mobilize and engage the regional ecosystems (L: SNN; P: ALL)

In Year 2, activities under Task 3.1 will focus on the full implementation of the Dance Floor methodology. The 12 Submissiond defined during the first period have evolved into 7 active Submission Groups (SMGs). These SMGs will take centre stage in WP3. Each SMG is a working group led by one region and coordinated by another one, with the participation of all ECIV partner regions according to their priority challenges.

Each SMG will refine its thematic focus, stakeholder composition, and expected outcomes, ensuring alignment with the Transformative Innovation Programme (TIP) and the priorities identified in WP2. The results from the Balland & Boschma mapping experiment will be integrated into the Dialogue Space to target potential interregional collaborations and identify synergies between regional value chains.

In the coming months new SGMs may be created to address some of the other interregional missions in coordination with WP2 and WP4 developments.

T3.2: Creating the “Challenge Space” to orient the connections towards collaborations in challenges (L: SNN; P: ALL)

Building on the Dialogue Space, the Challenge Space will become the key platform for defining and developing specific innovation challenges. The first series of interregional challenge-definition workshops will be held during this period, co-led by SNN and HURC. These workshops will convert the work of the SMGs into concrete challenge statements and draft project

concepts to be submitted under the first Open Call. The ECIV Matchmaking Platform will be fully integrated into this process, facilitating partner search, networking, and knowledge sharing across regions. Coordination between SNN, HURC, and WP4 will ensure that the challenges defined in this space align with the Open Call's scope and evaluation criteria.

T3.3: Development of interregional project concepts and preparation for the Open Call (L: SNN; P: ALL)

This new task will focus on supporting the translation of identified challenges into mature project proposals. WP3 will guide the SMGs through short design sprints to structure their ideas according to the Open Call templates developed in WP4. Coaching sessions and peer-review meetings will be organised to strengthen proposal quality, stakeholder balance, and innovation potential. The expected outcome is a first portfolio of 5–10 interregional project concepts ready for submission to the Open Call in December 2025. Lessons learned from this process will also inform updates to the Dance Floor methodology and serve as good-practice cases for replication in subsequent rounds.

WP4: Competitive selection and funding of interregional innovation projects (L: NOR) [M5 – M60]

T4.1: Open Call priorities definition (L: NOR; P: GN, DAL, SNN, IPF, IAL, SE)

This task is already completed concerning composition of CAB and topics of Open Call 1. Activities are planned for the upcoming months concerning Open Call 2, so that to refine the scope of the Call following the experience of Open Call 1.

T4.2: Preparation and management of Open Calls for Innovation Projects (L: NOR; P: ALL)

The primary focus of this period will be the launch, promotion, and management of Open Call 1. This will include the final validation of call documentation by the Call Steering Committee (CSC), the official opening of the submission platform, and the coordination of the evaluation and selection processes. The WP4 team will work closely with all partners to promote the call through targeted dissemination activities coordinated with WP6, ensuring wide participation across ECIV regions. Evaluators will be contracted through the framework established in Year 1, guaranteeing a transparent and high-quality assessment process. The Call Secretariat will oversee communication with applicants, provide guidance during the submission process, and prepare the results for approval by the CSC.

T4.3: Design and management of an Open Experimentation Fund for collaboration (L: SNN; P: ALL)

In parallel with the main Open Call, the Experimentation Fund will be fully activated during Year 2. The fund will support small-scale, early-stage collaborative initiatives that aim to test innovative ideas, feasibility studies, and proofs of concept in circular value chains. The governance structure defined in the previous period will be applied to evaluate and monitor funded experiments, ensuring complementarity with OC1. Calls for proposals will be open on a rolling basis, encouraging continuous participation from stakeholders. The results of the first funded experiments will be collected and analysed to inform WP2 and WP3 about emerging innovation patterns and ecosystem needs.

Task 4.4: Follow-up and monitoring of funded projects and funding activities (L: NOR; P: IPF, SNN, DAL, GN, IAL, MIGB, SE)

This task is starting at the end of year 2. First activities will be implemented in line with the process agreed within the year in D4.2 'evaluation templates', part 'Governance evaluation and ethics document'.

T4.5: Development and maintenance of tools as funding supporting activity (L: NOR; P: ALL)

The electronic submission and monitoring platform developed in Year 1 will become fully operational in this period. E-Mundus, the contracted IT provider, will oversee the platform's maintenance and user support during the first Open Call. Partners will receive training on how to use the system for evaluation, project tracking, and reporting. Additional functionalities will be added to enhance user experience, facilitate data collection, and integrate monitoring indicators aligned with ECIV's KPIs. This platform will also serve as a central repository for data and statistics on funded projects, supporting transparency and continuous improvement of ECIV's funding mechanisms.

WP5: Innovation Valley Results exploitation and replication. Roadmap for the future and outreach of new Circular Valleys (L: ACR+) [M24 – M60]

WP5 has not yet started its activities, which are scheduled to begin in the third year of the project. Therefore, no activities are planned for Year 2.

WP6: Dissemination and communication (Leader: IAL) [M1 – M60]

T6.1: Deployment of the detailed dissemination and communication plan (L: IAL; P: ALL)

The D&C Strategy will be reviewed and updated as planned and once approved will continue to guide all project communication efforts. The D&C Team will meet monthly to coordinate upcoming activities and ensure consistent messaging across regional and European channels. IAL will update the project's editorial calendar and communication toolkit, adding new materials related to the first Open Call and the Transformative Innovation Programme. Continuous internal training will be organised to strengthen partners' communication capacities, focusing on regional communication and visual consistency.

T6.2: Implementation of D&C activities to outreach ECIV's partners scope (L: IAL; P: ALL)

In Year 2, WP6 will intensify outreach through online and physical channels to support stakeholder mobilisation and participation in the Open Calls. Social media campaigns and website features will highlight success stories from regional ecosystems, early outcomes of the Dance Floor, and upcoming funding opportunities. The ECIV website will be expanded with new sections dedicated to the Open Calls, showcasing guidelines for applicants and news on awarded projects once available.

ECIV will continue to strengthen external visibility through its European networks, engaging with initiatives such as CCRI, Circular Flanders, and ERRIN. The project will be also represented at major policy events, positioning ECIV within the broader Regional Innovation Valleys agenda. IAL will maintain systematic monitoring of website traffic, social media performance, and media mentions to track engagement and optimise outreach strategies.

T6.3: Implementation of D&C activities in each ECIV region (L: IAL; P: ALL)

Regional communication and dissemination will play a central role in Year 2, with partners intensifying their local outreach efforts. Each region will organise or participate in events promoting ECIV's approach to circular innovation, such as regional forums, workshops, and

stakeholder meetings linked to the Dance Floor and the Open Calls. IAL will coordinate the creation of new multilingual promotional materials, including updated flyers, infographics, and short videos showcasing regional case studies. Special emphasis will be placed on increasing participation and visibility from partners that were less active in Year 1, ensuring balanced contributions across the consortium. These regional efforts will also feed into ECIV's European-level communication through consistent reporting and content sharing.

4.1.4. Continuous monitoring

Deliverables planned for Year 2

	Name	Lead	Due date	Description
D2.2	Transformative Innovation Programme, TIP	DAL	31.10.2025	Fact based intervention (TIP) via TIP and regional plans.
D2.3	Annual Work Plan Year 2	DAL	31.10.2025	Yearly annual work plan with the different regional and interregional activities
D2.4	Annual Work Plan Year 3	DAL	31.08.2026	Yearly annual work plan with the different regional and interregional activities
D2.8	Predefinition of modules & tools for capacity & capability building report	DAL	31.08.2026	Setting the possible and best practices of capacity and capability building tools and methods to use in WP3 including mobilizing workshops and seminars.
D2.9	Policy Innovation Platform	DAL	31.01.2025	Policy Innovation Platform established for TIP and multistakeholder policy mix mission-oriented actions.
D2.10	Regional Action plans	DAL	31.12.2025	Analysis of the main regional gaps on innovation and circular policies and proposal of activities to improve their regional policies and strategies
D3.1	Circular innovation ecosystems engagement whitebook	SNN	28.02.2026	Whitebook that defines and explains the methodology to create a "DIALOGUE SPACE" to mobilize and engage the regional ecosystems
D3.2	Circular innovation challenges on industrial value chains paper	SNN	31.08.2026	This document will explain the methodology to define the CI challenges targeting different value chains and the way to face those challenges.
D4.1	Open calls documents	NOR	31.10.2025	Comprised by (1) guidelines for applicants including the text of the call and evaluation criteria, (2) template for the sub-grantee agreement, (3) call

				leaflet, (4) application form for applicants, (5) Q&A section and (6) online microsite at the project website and platform
D4.2	Evaluation templates	NOR	01.01.2026	Instructions and templates to perform the evaluation of every proposal by the evaluators according to the defined criteria
D4.3	Contract with evaluators	NOR	01.03.2026	Contract to be signed by the coordinator and the external evaluators that will be hired
D4.4	Grant Agreement	NOR	01.03.2026	Template of the legal contractual document to be signed by selected third parties and the consortium

Milestones planned for Year 2

	Name	Lead	Due date
3	First regional plans delivered	DAL	31.12.2025
5	Submission of the OC documents	NOR	30.11.2025
6	1st Open call launched	NOR	31.12.2025

4.2. Participation in Annual Work Programme activities

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	YES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GN: Consultants for challenges of regional Circular Economy and contracts to connect stakeholders and boost the circular economy in the region in water food and packaging and for specialised support for financial and administrative management in WPI. €110,000. SODENA plan €32,000 for subcontracting associated with task 2.4 and approximately €14,000 for KPI methodology and preparatory action blocks, all of which is associated with the Valley Office (task 2.2). DAL will subcontract €7,000 for D2.2 (the TIP) including development of methods for MoI and Theories of Change. For D2.10, DAL anticipates subcontracting costs of approximately €2,000–€3,000. This includes support with system mapping and Theories of Change. NOR plans to allocate €60,000 to pay external evaluators for the OC. 	
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?	NO

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	NO
Does the participant envisage that part of the work is performed by associated partners (Article 9.1 of the MGA)?	NO

4.3. Resources to be committed

4.3.1. Summary effort table

WP	Title	Leader	Person Months	Start Month	End Month
1	Project management	GN	14,5	13	24
2	Design of transformative innovation program and regional action plans for circular for interconnected Regional Innovation Valleys	DAL	41,4	13	24
3	Creation of the Circular Economy "Dance Floor"	SNN	148,9	13	24
4	Competitive selection and funding of interregional innovation projects	NOR	33,7	13	24
5	Innovation Valley Results exploitation and replication. Roadmap for the future and outreachment of new Circular Valleys	ACR+	0	-	-
6	Dissemination and communication	IAL	19	13	24
Total PMs			257,5		

4.3.2. Summary effort table by beneficiary

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	Total PMs
1. GN	3	2	2	6	0	1	14
2. SODENA	6,5	8	5	2,5	0	2	24
3. SNN	0,5	1,2	5	1,6	0	0,4	8,7
4. GRO	0,1	0,8	3	0,8	0	0,4	5,1
5. FRY	0'1	0,8	3	0,8	0	0,4	5
6. DTH	0'1	0,8	3	0,8	0	0,4	5
7. UGRO	0'1	0,8	3	0	0	0,2	4
8. IPF	0'1	0,6	1,5	0	0	0,2	2,3
9. DAL	0,4	3	4	1,4	0	0,8	9,6
10. VAR	0,3	2	4	1,4	0	0,6	8,3

11. GAV	0,3	2	4	1,4	0	0,6	8,3
12. NOR	1	5	6	9	0	1	22
14. SPW	0,2	2	5	0	0	1	8,2
15. IAL	0,6	5	5	4	0	5	19,6
16. HURC	0,2	2	3	0	0	1	6,2
17. SE	0,6	4	5	4	0	1	14,6
18. IBioIC	0,6	1	87	0	0	1	89,6
19. ACR+	0,2	0,4	0,4	0	0	2	3
Total PMs	14,5	41,4	148,9	33,7	0	19	257,5

4.3.3. 'Purchase costs' items (travel and subsistence, equipment and other goods, works and services)

1. GN		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	24,500	This budget is allocated to prepare project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Financial Support for Third Parties	2,522,500	Funds allocated to the 1 st Open Call
Total	2,553,000	

2. SODENA		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	11,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	3,000	This budget is allocated to regional events.
Total	14,000	

3. SNN		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
66000/Other goods, works and services	4,500	This budget is allocated to organise regional events and dissemination costs, etc
Financial Support for Third Parties	1,200,000	Funds allocated to the 1 st Open Call
Total	1,208,500	

4. GRO		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2,600	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	4,000	This budget is allocated to organise regional events and dissemination costs, etc
Total	6,600	

5. FRY		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2,600	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	4,000	This budget is allocated to organise regional events and dissemination costs, etc
Total	6,600	

6. DTH		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2,600	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	4,000	This budget is allocated to organise regional events and dissemination costs, etc
Total	6,600	

7. UGRO		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2,500	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	3,000	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Total	5,500	

8. IPF		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1,700	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	1,000	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Total	2,700	

9. DAL		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	3,100	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Financial Support for Third Parties	444,444	Funds allocated to the 1 st Open Call
Total	451,544	

10. VAR		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	3,100	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Financial Support for Third Parties	444,444	Funds allocated to the 1 st Open Call
Total	451,544	

11. GAV		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	3,100	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Financial Support for Third Parties	444,444	Funds allocated to the 1 st Open Call
Total	451,544	

12. NOR		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	24,500	This budget is allocated to organise regional events and dissemination costs, and also the payments relative to the creation on the OC platform.
Financial Support for Third Parties	2,073,938	Funds allocated to the 1 st Open Call
Total	2,104,438	

14. SPW		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	2,000	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Total	6,600	

15. IAL		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	10,500	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Total	16,500	

16. HURC		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	2,600	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Total	6,600	

17. SE		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	7,000	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Financial Support for Third Parties	2,000,000	Funds allocated to the 1 st Open Call
Total	2,013,000	

18. IBioIC		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Other goods, works and services	10,800	This budget is allocated to perform project meetings, regional events, dissemination costs, etc
Total	16,800	

19. ACR+		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6,000	Total costs divided per 5 years
Total	6,000	